

Transcription of Interview 9

November 2020

Shane: ..of the National Health Insurance. So there's no sort of scripted answer, but more to get what your impression and engagement with it, has been. So there's only four questions, the first question is, rather broadly, what is your views of the NHI?

Interview 9: Views, specifically.. to what? Because, remember, with NHI, it's **specifically for different reasons**.. but more as a healthcare provider, in terms of service delivery?

Shane: If we can explore all of them, so perhaps your view, as a service provider.

Interview 9: Look, for me, my view with NHI is, government hasn't engaged a lot in terms of community **basis**, so that people understand what this is bringing and what will people benefit out of it; a lot of people, they don't understand. So I feel that it is more relevant to the clinical **people**... NHI is addressing the community, but they didn't **engage so that people will understand how**. So I **think** that they **need** more community **engagement**, **if** that is done, even ourselves, as healthcare **providers**, **there are** still other **questions** to **understand**. In my case, the.. I don't want to say **programme**, but ja, market the **strategy**, because there's quite a lot of clarity that we also need to get. For instance, aware that there is another **policy** where NHI is speaking at working with the private sector. So how will it work out with the public / private **departments**?

So those are the things that, even ourselves, is still not very clear, how it is going to work out. We know that there will be resources in the private sector, on services that we, as a department, wouldn't be able to offer, but the whole process, is still not clear; so those are the things that I'm saying. I believe that government should **get input** and **grow** the community awareness, and still engage us as **healthcare** service providers.

Shane: Okay. And speaking about that sort of engagement and awareness, you've mentioned that you feel that government hasn't engaged too well. Is there any events, or contact, that you've received from government, to give input or insight?

Interview 9: What **happened** ja, I don't remember, I think it was this year, where there were community **participation**, so we were invited to go, **and** I think it was in Soweto, **community hall**, that we were invited; so the MEC and the **ministers**, **it was the political figures**, they came, there was a presentation, but it was different sectors, so obviously, there was **labour**, there was just different sectors; so if you are in that environment, labour is **talking** labour policy, where they feel that people are exploited and everything. So I **felt** that there was a Professor, who did quite a **very good presentation**, but I felt that the audience, a **sector** of the audience, also, even the questions and everything, was **diluting the quality of the message**; so they could have **told you the plan** properly, so that **we can develop our focus**.

[05:03]

So, as much as we were engaged, I came out of there still feeling that I really didn't get much; it was the **overview**, you **understand**; government policy, and obviously, they are trying to **add** to that **there is urgency**, and the health system is **trying**.

But I heard that the **engagement**, maybe they could have.. because **that meeting** was like three hours, so I heard that maybe they could have had a follow-up, or that **the insight through a pre-meeting**, and **I mean**, then **we** will inform them how much we know about NHI, and then after, then we can do it.. **I mean**, they sponsor it for free, we can do it on our **own**, do it **together**, and then it will give them an idea in terms of how they structure and a kind of update on NHI. So **they** have been, but it was only once.

Shane: Okay. And with regards to getting information around the developments, or processes of the NHI, how do you, mainly, get your information? Is there a specific channel that you use? Or do you rely more on mainstream media?

Interview 9: For me, it is out of curiosity where you will **Google**, but you don't have like a **formal** standard, where you get updates. Sometimes from the government communications, it will be, but it's not done regular, where you'll get the information as **frequent as.. it's just once in a while**; because I feel that government are **tending** to focus a lot on covid, and we're getting, almost every week, you get something from **commentators** about covid. So they can do that, even with NHI, so that **upon reading**, we understand. But we really.. there isn't much that is, frequently, sent to us, as healthcare workers, to read and understand what NHI's all about; and even our role in the whole sector.

Shane: Okay. And with regards to the funding of the NHI, they're wanting to sort of separate the funder from the provider; and so district health management offices that would receive money, and then pay that out to, either public or private sector; do you see that as a successful, or useful means?

Interview 9: Ja, at the moment, I can't say it will **be**, but remember, it hasn't been.. I know that there were pilots and.. everything, but even the proper reports from what came out of the pilot, it was not made.. maybe it's out there, we're having.. we've been **ignoring** that, but for me, since the **recent budget** cut, the district... obviously, **you need** enough resources, and **verysmart** people, because I think you've taken those that, already, our province, like in the PPE scandal; so obviously, you need people with values and people with ethics, that would be able to manage this, but at a district level. And when that happens, and you see the impact, then we can start **appreciating** the decentralisation of the **NHI**.

But at the moment, because it hasn't happened, we are.. I don't think one can comment; all that we know, when everything is centralised at the provincial office, and **with regarding** getting **state approval**, and even when they decentralise, they decentralise in such a way that the **limitation**, in terms of **expenditure**. And so, in such a way, they it still **addresses** the problem, to continue with other **efforts**. So ja, it hasn't happened at the moment, and obviously, the pilot **studies** are the ones that could better respond, because they would have had insight on how is it really **works**.

[10:33]

Shane: Okay. And what would you suggest, as the best way to fund the National Health Insurance? Have you had any thought around that?

Interview 9: Look, I haven't had.. so, like I **never had** that engagement, that is where **we need** dialogue, so I **can wrap** my thoughts around it, because I understand **it as**, medical aids are not going to be applicable, so obviously, the government's supposed to be funding this, and obviously, we are saying government, but it's tax payers money which is going to be managed through Treasury. So I'm not a **finance person** per say, so I wouldn't really.. unless I fully understand NHI, as the whole supply chain, **obviously**, I don't think that it will be really **clear** how it's supposed to be funded. But I understand the government **strategy**, and obviously, government **needs resources**, but I'm not sure, at what level or **how** we will have to contribute in funding the whole **programme**.

Shane: Yes, okay. And you mentioned working with the private sector, what are your views? Do you think that would be useful? Do you think it will be a challenge?

Interview 9: So at the moment, I didn't give a **thought to** approach, as at the level in my **programme**, what we are doing, we are.. it's like the provincial office is **doing something** and they are doing **things for us** for us, **they are paying them**, and then the other **programme also be contracting** their own offering, **providing** to the community; obviously, there's a programme that they did, to follow and comply and then they get paid for that; so, as a pilot.

So we **did** have some **sort of a insight** on how we will manage private sector, when they will partner with government, because our experience with **private doctors that are contracted** by government, they don't understand government systems, especially when it comes to finance and payments, so they become very frustrated. Also, as the department report, **electronic** reporting systems, that is standard for the entire country, that they **did use**, they used their own private sector, **made up** system, and when we get to link them to the government systems, it's a little bit frustrating, because, obviously, we have to monitor it. And they are not used to being monitored, because remember, their **work** is their **functioning**. So there's a little bit of frustration, because obviously, we need to also do our due diligence, and make sure that before we pay them, we have identified ourselves, and from my **programme**, we maintain and **try** to align ourselves with the **payment**, and quality of.. making sure that we pay them **within the** date of the **payment** that has been submitted.

But before we do that, obviously, **there are checks and balances** that we do **with** them, because they're used to sending their medical aid, and medical aid will pay, because they use a **code**. Whereas we ask, **can** you validate on our system, where the department can be able to **validate** that information.

[15:21]

So I find they're a little bit frustrated, but as they get used to it, then they are **better**. So for me, that can then inform us, in terms of how we can work with them, because there is a cohort of doctors, they can **see** how we can better improve our communication, our interactions, our processes, because they are quite used to doing things the private way. They don't follow policy, they do things out of protocol, so we have to **[..]** them, just make sure that they comply.

So there's a lot of monitoring that's involved, because in the private sector, you do as you wish, because there is no gatekeeping; whereas with us, we've got protocols and policies that guide the **practice**, whether it's **treatment, or basic management**. So that **transition**.. I have noticed that a lot of **practices**, because they're not used to people telling them what to do, people reminding them of policy, they just do as they **please**.

So it's a process that's doable, but you're going to see a lot of gatekeeping, for people to get used to how government system works; and obviously, there is an opportunity to improve, and it's a two-way system; they **give us the** policy and we come to a common understanding. But I believe that public and private sector, we can still work together, it's just that **it needs to be well-defined**; and also the **interpretation** of policy, because if we're talking **primary care**, there is a person that we need to refer to, a doctor within the private sector, **what happens with the processes?** What is the **communication**? All these algorithms, that we comply.

So I still believe that it's doable, but it's going to be a lot of work to be done. So for me, it wouldn't be ideal that **implementation**, it will be better that we **collaborate** with a small group of private sector, **they need to put their thoughts out**.

Shane: Okay. And with regards.. shifting to the public service, do you think that the public service is ready to implement a scheme as large as the NHI?

Interview 9: Ah, look, one thing I believe, that if you don't try, you never do, **you are ready**. So if public sector can start on a small scale, and like I'm saying, the lessons learnt can then improve how things can be better approached. But I predict that they are significant, **data of** experience, because that.. **working** the private sector, they can bring valuable input. But in terms of the entire system, I'm not so.. I cannot say we are ready, or we are not ready, but I will propose that we **start**; and then, more or less, scale-up approach. When we get it right here, then we increase more stakeholders, or whatever that we will be doing; even clinics, we start with twenty, and when we get it right, then we add just like that, up until we have completed all.

But the **problem**.. I don't think it will help, because we'll never know the capacity, we'll never know the **big issue** that needs to be addressed.. So we might as well just start, because the government, it's not like it's going to go away, it has to be implemented, but obviously, with a will and with an open mind of learning and correcting. But obviously, the learning shouldn't be **financially, and costing** patient's life, also. **So some of these things need to be balanced**.

[20:35]

Shane: Yes. And in your opinion and your experience, with managerial issues, what would you say are the challenges that health service managers would experience, when implementing the National Health Insurance?

Interview 9: Look, what people **do**.. why the department also needs to strengthen.. the level of accountability, that needs to be strengthened, and also, systems should be in place for **consequence** management. And obviously, the monitoring part of it should be embedded, and it's also one skill that

not most of the managers have; the monitoring skill, and the other difficult aspect of **this**. So people can be supported, they can be guided, but if ever you don't have a consequence management approach, and accountability, things can just **fall** through, without anybody really paying attention or taking responsibility. So those things need to be filtered, especially on the management level, to make sure that service delivery is there, and good quality care, **are appropriate**.

Because, for me, we've got programmes that are looking at quality, and efficacy, but when you look at outcomes, the outcomes, they don't match the level of **classification**. So there is a programme that talked about ideal clinic, and then the ideal clinic, the clinic that are, and then they are put.. and I think **speaking** also, one of the strategies was NHI.

So the facilities, then, will be categorised at a certain level, because they grade them according to goals **and standards apply criteria**. So there will be a facility that is at the highest level of grading, but when you look at **patient** quality of care, and health outcomes, they don't match the grading. So those are the things that we should also be taking cognisance, and that is the other difficult aspect that I'm referring to, that I also feel that it's lacking on both of the managers; that we cannot be **happy** that we've got X number of facilities that are at **enough standard**, but when you look at the **communities** around those clinics, the outcomes are talking. So it is more compliance in terms of **administration**, but **basic** management is not at the platinum level. So those are the other concerns, for me, that obviously need to be filtered in, when they roll out NHI.

Shane: Okay. And how would you suggest improving that management, and getting better outcomes with greater accountability? What have you seen, that works? Or what could you think of?

Interview 9: Listen, you know, it's not actually a one size fits for all, it depends on the circumstances, the programme, as a unit. But for me, it's not **as if** we've got an accountability that.. we've got **skills**, we've got people that are **working around this problem**, because for me, if you've got insight on what NHI aims to achieve, and you are able to plan and market it, then you are able to come back and monitor it, but obviously, **tools** to be put in place, to assess are give feedback, in terms of observations and outcomes.

[25:38]

So ja, I.. look, with government, more or less, as it is, that is there, normally, in the health unit, we would be told that, not everything will be solved by NHI, so that is why I'm saying that the accountability element of our leader, and understand, and also having buy-in in the rollout of this programme, it's important. But even the political will to make sure that NHI happens, and investing resources, because at the moment, if you look at our facilities, they **are not close to being** addressed and able to accommodate. I mean, from the resource **that** a level, our facilities are not ready. From resource allocation, there's a **hell** lot of **redtape**, and I mean, I think you heard that the Minister of Finance speaking **about finances.. he was just saying that we would keep our numbers the same**, and start recruitment for the next **three** years. So **at least** we will work with what we have. Already, you've got an **overwhelming workload** where we need more **processes**.

So those are the things that need to be filtered in. If you're **happy and so you start to implement**. So you need to have those systems put in place, that will be able to do the checks and balances. But if you've got **a used** and already overstressed system, it's like you're doing the same thing over and over, and expecting a different outcome.

Shane: Okay. And then, Mrs Interview 9, the last question, rather broadly, is there any other view or thought that you would like to express about the NHI?

Interview 9: Ja, **I would be happy** if.. The way the department is bombarding us with **covid**; because we copy the way they are giving us information on how to wear the mask properly, the **difference**, and **they provide** information for those who need it. But the NHI, it's information that is **vague, and incomplete** and the department is just **not** using community engagement and **such**.

But when they use this platform where they send communication to all, and then we get it in our phone, we get it on our email, then one get to read, and **it make** sense, and kind of align ourselves, that, by the way, I'm part of the NHI rollout, this is what is expected, this is the approach that the department is giving, but we're not getting much from the department. Unless you come to there, where you're lucky, you can get it; but in the era of covid, where we **cannot introducing a paper**, then they need to use electronic mail to communicate with us, and nothing too much, reading, but that's a basic in terms of a bulk SMS, in terms of emails that we get, in terms of the... - no, its a little bit academic - but the normal internet communication platforms that they use.

[30:14]

And obviously, it can be **attending**, again, in management meetings, where **three** Directors are forced to ensure that every meeting, there is an agenda on NHI, to force us, as junior managers, to engage, to collaborate, and also understand **that** there are misconceptions about interpreting what NHI aims to achieve.

So those engagements, and also feedback loop, that needs to go back to the department, that this is **[..] abuse** of their healthcare professionals, this is **abuse of their political**, and that's.. when it gets to the department, that we get a response, where the feedback's **acknowledged**, and somebody saying, I'm hearing you, healthcare providers, I'm hearing you, and this is the clarity and the position that we are taking, as government.

Shane: Okay. Then Mrs Interview 9, from my side, that's everything. Thanks very much for your time, and making a space for us to have the interview. You've really provided some valuable insights into managerial challenges with NHI.

Interview 9: Okay. Thank you very much.

Shane: And once I've converted the interview into Microsoft word format, I'll just send it back to you, so you could review it, if you would like, and then any changes you would like to make, you can just let me know.

Interview 9: Okay. Not a problem.

Shane: Alright, thanks again for your time.

Interview 9: Okay, thanks, hey.

Shane: Thanks, bye.

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